

Electromagnetic Heating and Intermetallic Compound Formation in Transient Inductive Chip-Level Bonding Using SnCuSn Foil for Microelectronic Applications

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This study presents a combined experimental and finite element (FE) simulation-based study on intermetallic compound (IMC) formation during transient inductive chip-level bonding using SnCuSn foil for microelectronic packaging applications. The objective is to investigate the behavior of localized heating and the subsequent phase evolution under rapid electromagnetic (EM) excitation. A copper (Cu) coil is used to selectively heat the bonding region, enabling the formation of the intermetallic phases Cu_6Sn_5 and Cu_3Sn , as confirmed through metallographic analysis.

Figure 1 illustrates the schematic structure of the power electronics module and bonding setup, including the copper coil and bonding interface. Finite element simulations, carried out in COMSOL Multiphysics, were used to model the electromagnetic heating profile and subsequent temperature-driven phase evolution. These simulations provide insight into transient heat distribution and intermetallic growth, as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Schematic structure of a power electronics module in accordance to [1].

Fig. 2. FE simulation of intermetallic formations of Cu and Sn.

Experimental trials were performed to validate the simulation results by controlling heating parameters and analyzing the resulting IMC formation through metallographic characterization. The strong correlation between the simulation and experimental outcomes confirms the effectiveness of this method for achieving localized, rapid, and robust bonding. This approach is particularly well-suited for thermally sensitive microelectronic systems that require minimal heat impact on adjacent components.

[1] Chironjeet Chaki, Manoshi Chaki, Keya Roy. Development of a Simplistic Method to Simulate the Formation of Intermetallic Compounds in Diffusion Soldering Process. American Journal of Materials Synthesis and Processing. Vol. 4, No. 1, pp. 54-61 (2019)